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A BLACK FUNGUS-MUCORMYCOSIS-POST COVID-19 COMPLICATIONS

Dr. Dhanapal Venkatachalam,

Sree Sastha Pharmacy College, Sree Sastha Nagar, Chembarambakkam, Chennai-600123.

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ABSTRACT

Human to human transmitted disease is the game of corona virus disease (COVID-19) transmission and it had been declared an emergency global pandemic that caused major disastrous in respiratory system to more than five million people and killing more than half a billion deaths across the globe. Besides lower acute respiratory syndrome, there is damage to alveolar with severe inflammatory exudation. COVID-19 patients often have lower immunosuppressive CD4+ T and CD8+ T cells and most patients in intensive care units (ICU) need mechanical ventilation, hence longer stay in hospitals. These patients have been discovered to develop fungal co-infections. COVID-19 patients develop what is known as mucormycosis a black fungal infection which is deadly leading to loss of sight and hearing and eventually death. This chapter will focus on mucormycosis, black fungus caused during post Covid 19 complications.

Corresponding author

Dr. Dhanapal Venkatachalam

Principal

Sree Sastha College Of Pharmacy,

Chennai –Bangalore High Way,

Chembarambakkam, Chennai – 600123

vddpaul@gmail.com

+ 919443952113

+91-7904937309

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INTRODUCTION

Mucormycosis (previously known as Zygomycosis) is a serious but rare fungal infection caused by a group of moulds known as Micromycetes. Rhino-orbital-cerebral-mucormycosis (ROCM) is caused by moulds of the order Mucorales. In this, there are a few subgroups like Rhizopus, Mucor, and Rhizomucor which are most commonly involved in this infection. These fungi are angioinvasive i.e, they invade the surrounding blood vessels and destroy them resulting in tissue necrosis and death. These moulds live throughout the environment and their spores are present in the air. They get lodged in the nasal cavity and adjoining sinuses. On reaching a favourable milieu they ensconce themselves within the tissue. The spores germinate, hyphae (filamentous processes) outgrow and release destructive juices which digest the host tissue and provide nutrition to the rapidly growing fungi. As they grow in the nasal cavity they relentlessly destroy the surrounding host tissue. The bones in the nasal cavity and sinuses are destroyed. These include the hard palate, the orbital bones, and the skull base bones. Black masses may be seen in the nasal cavity and oral cavity. If it destroys the orbit and enters the eye socket it may cause bulging of the eyes, pain, frozen eye movements, and blindness. Once it enters the cranial cavity by breaching the skull base it blocks major arteries and venous lakes resulting in major life-threatening brain strokes and bleeds. The spores can sometimes travel into the depths of the respiratory system and get comfortably lodged in the lung parenchyma (alveoli and bronchioles). Here the fungi grow rapidly, destroying the lung tissue and compromising blood oxygenation. From there it can spread into the circulatory system resulting in an existential crisis. A fungal pathogen called *Aspergillus* cause devastating disease in immune compromised hosts. These hosts include haematological malignancies due to fungus being air borne, they cause wreck to lungs guarding frontline defence. Severe viral pulmonary have risen and given birth to pulmonary aspergilliosis (IPA). Most cases are IPA with 7-23% associated with fatality ¹ This IPA is compared to triple strain corona causing wreckage to lower respiratory tract infections leading to acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). Triple strain corona is considerably high on patients those are in need of ICU furthering them to suffer from mucormycosis. Hence fatality rate is estimated to be high ² below is the figure of mucormycosis under LPCB mount ²

Figure 1: Figure of Mucormycosis Under LPCB Mount.

Case to Further Study

There is a report of 7 cases with mucormycosis. They were previously diagnosed with obstructive chronic pulmonary disease (OCPD) with symptoms of obstructive sleep apnea, insulin dependent diabetes, retinopathy, nephropathy, polyneuropathy. Severe other ones include coronary heart disease and arterial hypertension. ³ Three out of seven patients were in the age group of 60-80 and four in age category of 30-60. One of the patients with age above 60 presented with productive cough, intermittent fever, dyspnoea for two weeks ⁴ Medical records displayed white blood cells count was less than normal, C-reactive protein (CRP) elevated (35 mg/dl; upper limit norm 5 mg/dl), D- dimer at normal range. Chest x-ray revealed bilateral basal coarse reticular opacities. RT-PCR (Real Time Polymerised Chain Reaction) from oropharyngeal swab was positive for corona. ⁵ Patient admitted to ICU, showed further deterioration and hypoxemia (pO₂ 46mmHg). There was high level of Creatinine, elevated neutrophils, CRP levels showed 140mg/dl, white blood cells still elevated (12.75*10⁹ per L) interleukins-6 was at 365ng/ml and ferritin 450ng/ml, only lymphocytes were normal. ⁶

Upon second day admission in ICU, patient was further intubated and mechanically ventilated. Chest x-ray revealed progression in bilateral infiltrates with pulmonary deterioration. Further stay in ICU, endotracheal aspiration was obtained from patient and culture test was done ⁷ Culture grew *Aspergillus fumigatus* voriconazole with fungal like growth. Lateral flow device reacted to *Aspergillus* specific antigen but none colonised. Serum fungal markers showed positive signs of black fungal growth. Galactomanna and 1,3- beta-D-glucan marker was used to detect the fungal growth. This fungal growth was subjected to treatment, despite of efforts the patient deceased on fifth day in ICU ⁸ Mucormycosis is very deadly causing loss of eyesight, hearing impair and severe heart attack and brain cell loss. All seven patients in different age groups, mild or harsh fungal infection have died ⁹

Fungal Infection after Covid-19

To put to the fact, fungal infection, Chen et al. performed this infection test in China on 99 patients out of which 5/99 were found having *Aspergillus flavus* and one case of *Candida glabrata* and three cases of *C. albicans*. After extensive search and study on mucormycosis and with little or no result of journals on this deadly fungus, one search result lead to another researcher, Yang et.al found little higher percentage of people affected by this disease¹⁰ Many patients were treated with antifungal medicine but were in vain. Another German study associated with COVID-19 found 6 out of 19 patients infected with black fungal. In Netherlands, there were fresh new cases of black fungus, infecting 7 with *A.fumigatus*.. In France there were 5 patients infected with *A. flavus* by tracheal aspirates culture¹¹ Many incidences in that period have found covid10 with fungal infection increase from 16- 27%, with severely ill patients dying. Most percentage of them with mucormycosis has died since the beginning on this fungal incidence began. Below figure shows penicillin in mucormycosis¹²

Figure 2: Figure Shows Penicillin in Mucormycosis.

One report also suggested that despite of IPA on fungal infection the mortality rate has increased from 23% to 51%. Clinically many patients are subjected to the fungal testing attributing to severe respiratory symptoms. Some diagnosis like antibiotics has delayed this fungus. It is critical to pay attention to this mucormycosis in current COVID-19 patients. Below is the figure of *Aspergillus flavus*¹³

Reasons for occurring COVID 19 Patients

Mucormycosis can occur any time after COVID-19 infection, either during the hospital stay or several days to a couple of weeks after discharge. “The COVID-19 causes favourable alteration in the internal milieu of the host for the fungus and the medical treatment given, unwittingly also abets fungal growth. COVID-19 damages the airway mucosa and blood vessels. It also causes an increase in the serum iron which is very important for the fungus to grow. Medications like steroids increase blood sugar. Broad-spectrum antibiotics not only wipe out the potentially pathogenic bacteria but also the protective commensals. Antifungals like Voriconazole inhibit Aspergillosis but *Mucor* remains unscathed and thrives due to lack of competition. Long-term ventilation reduces immunity and there are speculations of the fungus being transmitted by the humidifier water being given along with oxygen. All the above make for a perfect recipe for mucormycosis infection.

Figure 3: Figure of *Aspergillus Flavus*.

DISCUSSION FOR DIAGNOSIS

It has been understood that black fungus called mucormycosis is complicating the treatment and recovery of COVID-19 patients. There were several reports of patients with invasive aspergillosis and positive growth of *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Aspergillus-abe* in endotracheal aspirate¹⁴. Many patients tested has two week history of COVID-19 before and after admission in ICU, a CT scan a valuable tool for corona patients revealed, slight mold infections in chest region, but slight reversible halo, ground glass opacities also observed in some. Patients with severe influenza or halo or reversible halo show pulmonary mould leading to mucormycosis¹⁵ to take a step further on discussion, a diagnostic setup is suggested. The discrimination between colonization and infection were put to test. With *Aspergillus* specific LFD and certified point assay. Test showed negative to colonisation but positive to infection. The result also shows growing hyphae during invasion of fungus¹⁶. Serum Galactomannan shows no sensitivity in non-neutropenia patients. The LFD is the recommended method for diagnosis of invasive aspergillosis. The benefit of GM screening in COVID-19 patients shows data that attracts attention on recently published trial. The data shows GM in serum is on the rise¹⁷. The new norms of European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer/Mycoases Study Group showed diagnostic criteria for ICU patients due to missing host. The criteria broadly includes chest imaging of lungs and microbiological evidence of *Aspergillus* presence. Presently the influenza and aspergillosis trial shows GM in serum and Broncho alveolar lavage fluid in mycological criterion to overcome imperfect culture limitation and sensitivity of *Aspergillus*. Below is the chart for colonisation¹⁸

Figure 4: The Chart for Colonization.

The patient reported presence of fungus, increasing the risk for IPA. Viral infections like influenza or cytomegalovirus infections increase risk for IPA. There is over expression of anti-inflammatory cytokines, T-helper cells and cell mediated immune response which is impaired. This impairment is due to mould in COVID-19 patients admitted to ICU. Hence discussion concludes IPA occurrence in COVID-19 patients¹⁹

Etymology and Diagnosis

It has been discovered that mucormycosis has common agents such as Rhizopusspp, Mucorspp. Genera of Mucorales, varies from country to country. Mucorspp, Lichthemiaspp and Rhizopussppat 34%, 19% and 19% are common in Europe. In India Rhizopusspp is the most common causing disease Apophysomyceselegans, A. variables and Rhizopushomothallius are emerging. Another species namely Apophysomyces reported in Mexico. By inhalation of sporangiospores, mucormycosis is caused¹⁹ these are air borne or direct inoculation of organisms into skin or gastrointestinal tract mucosa. Recent studies suggest they are seasonal infections occurring from August to November, but patients in Australia showed mucormycosis occurring anytime with uncommon species such as non Rhizopus and some infected with Apophysomyces or Sakenaspp localised in skin and tissues²⁰ Mucormycosis has been a centre of attention all around the globe. But there seem difference in species and effect on human body differing from developed country and developing nations. In developed nation this disease is less common and seen only in patients with haematological malignancies (HM). The developing countries paint a different picture, it is common is patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus or trauma. In India, mucormycosis is seen in 14 out of 100000 patients. In Europe and US it is seen in 0.01 per 100000 population²¹

Figure 5: The Image of Formation of Mucormycosis Inside.

The percentage associated with mucormycosis in rhino-orbito- cerebral pulmonary are 27%, 20% and 18% . In Europe it is 27%, 32%, 26%. Considering patients with HM is less compared to patients in India with DM. In Mexico, 72% of people were associated with diabetes underlying malignancies, sinus and pulmonary. Below is the figure for diagnosis of mucormycosis²² Infections from Mucorales are usually rapid, they were initially reported in farmers from China. Some reports show they are opportunistic fungus like Mucor irregularis, that has completely different epidemiology. Their infections are highly chronic but without any risk factors effecting only skin and tissue cells²³.

Figure 6: The Figure For Diagnosis of Mucormycosis.

Fungal isolates such as Rhizopusspp and Lichthemiasppa long with Mucorspp were found in children in some cases. Keeping the factors of HM and malignancies such as solid organ transplant, surgery, DM and underlying many medical conditions the fungus targets the above and attacks lungs, skin, soft tissues, sino orbital and rhino cerebral region. Mortality rate for such studies were more than 60%. In Children it was 15% with certain infection²³

Clinical Diagnosis and Possibilities

The diagnosis has prerequisite and with great deal of suspicion and recognition host, we can incur to conclusion through testing methodologies such as histology, imaging modalities, advanced molecular methods and microbiology. As a revision, rhinocerebral pulmonary is the most common clinical presentation for Mucorales with representation in soft tissues, pulmonary vessels, disseminated diseases and any other organ that shows infection [24]. Tissue necrosis is the benchmark for mucormycosis. Fungi such as *Aspergillus* or *Fusarium* show some sign. Below chart shows pathophysiology of mucormycosis²⁴

Figure 7: Chart Shows Pathophysiology of Mucormycosis.

In many countries where tuberculosis is relevant, two infections coexist. However with diabetic patients the index is higher for invasive pulmonary mucormycosis. The list that should be considered as symptoms are cranial nerve palsy, diplopia, sinus pain, orbital apex syndrome, ulcer, preorbital swelling. In radiology, most common symptom is pleural effusion. Computerised topography (CT) scan that indicates mucormycosis is the reverse halo sign (RHS), when sequential thoracic CT scans are performed in more than 100 patients RHS were observed in 92 patients during initial stage of disease. Hence we conclude RHS on CT scan is a strong indicator of presence of pulmonary mucormycosis. In another study of patients with lung mucormycosis, presence of RHS is common on all of them. Symptoms were centrilobular nodules, bronchial wall thickening, peribronchial consolidation with *Aspergillus* in it. Another method for aggressive lab technique to identify mucormycosis is positron emission tomography-computed tomography (PET/CT) with fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG). Endo brachial ultrasound guided injection is the best and useful diagnostic tool for mucormycosis²⁵

Figure 8: Graph Shows Presence on Mucormycosis and Growth.

Laboratory Work and Culture Technique

Laboratory work and culture on petri dish is the effective clinical tool for mucormycosis. Below is the microscopic view of mucormycosis²⁵

Figure 9: Microscopic view of mucormycosis.

Hypea and Mucorales have a width of 6-25 Nano meters and are nonseptate and have a ribbon shaped appearance. The angle and branching are at 90 degrees and fungal element is seen at hematoxylin and eosin regions. To elevate morphology more, periodic acid Schiff or Grocott were used for silver staining to highlight hypea. Tissue hispathology shows inflammation regions, in some cases these are absent in immune suppressed patients. In cases of nerve cells, perineural invasion is present when done by tissue histopathology, but that is not the best method always, tissue differentiation is most effective to differentiate between hypea of Aspergillus and hypea of Mucorales. It distinguishes all fungi and helps in pathogen of specimen in laboratory culture containment²⁶

It is observed that Mucorales grow upto 3-7 days on fungal media, namely potato dextrose agar and Sabouraud agar incubated at 25 degrees. In some cases, it aids in yield of culture, because hyphae are friable in nature and gets damaged easily. The main target of this culture in situ hybridization is 5s and 18s ribosomal RNA sequence, hence a specific mouse monoclonal anti- Rhizo mucorantibody is employed to target analysis and to react strongly on mucorales and Entomophthorales²⁷

Identification of Species

Identifying species is more important for better understanding of epidemiology of mucormycosis. Mucorales fungi differentiates from Aspergillus fungi on culture and provides high level of accuracy in fungal identification. Test kits used are ID32C combined with positive melezitose assimilation detects *L.remosa*. Another one is thematrix assisted laser desorption/isolation time of flight (MALDI-TOF) along with mass spectrometry [28]. Serology used are ELISA assays immunoblots and immunodiffusion tests that are invasive towards Mucorales and mucormycosis. Specific T cells were detected from above, they are used as surrogate diagnostic markers for further research. Molecular assays such as PCR restriction fragment length polymorphism analysis (RFLP), DNA sequencing of defined genes and melt curve analysis were part of assays that help in analysis of Mucorales. They targeted internal transcribes 18s rRNA genes²⁹

Specificity in Cure

Multimodal approach is necessary to cure mucormycosis. Early dosage of anti-fungal agents, rapid correction of metabolic abnormalities are mandatory features. For diabetic patients, sodium bicarbonate (with insulin) to reverse ketoacidosis regardless of whether acidosis is mild or severe, has the ability to reverse Mucorales to invade hosts.

Drugs such as corticosteroids should help in early diagnosis such as to stop tissue invasion. Mucormycosis has characteristics to invade blood vessel that leads to thrombosis and tissue necrosis. The suggestion by European conference for such harsh invasion is lipid formulation of amphotericin B. The suggested dose is 5mg/kg/day upto 10mg/kg/day for injection in central nervous system. The results conducted on patients with mucormycosis showed a response rate of 78% in week 1 to 87% on week 12.³⁰ Posaconazole and isavuconazole are used as maintenance therapy dosages recommended by ECMM at dose of 200 mg q6h of oral. This has some effect on fungus and recovery rate is high. Another option is salvage treatment, combining effects of liquid amphotericin B and caspofungin or posaconazole, impact showed survival rates much higher on patients with rhino orbital cerebral mucormycosis. The use of hyperbaric oxygen to enrich cytokine environment to lower fungal cell area works at high percentage. This oxygen helps in stimulating granulocyte- macrophage colony giving way for interferon gamma response to fight the Mucorales. Final treatment can be done with the usage of drug VT-1161, an inhibitor with selective activity against fungus. They are ergosterol synthesis inhibitor and prove an additional asset to fight mucormycosis³¹

CONCLUSION

Mucormycosis is a disease that is rare but poses an important burden on immune compromised patients. Newly developed medications have several pathogenesis but cure to mucormycosis is still a challenge. Several methods have delayed the mortality but still poses a challenge in curing mucorales. The clinical presentation is nonspecific, and early diagnosis target the histopathology efficiency and it is time consuming. Direct examination of culture, molecular diagnostic techniques, PCR and situ hybridisation offer an alternate to initiation the treatment. The management of mucormycosis depends on underlying factors such as injection of antifungal agents, surgical intervention and timely dosage of antifungal therapy. Immunologic and metabolic profiling is the way to approach this black fungus i.e mucormycosis.

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